

Supplementary materials for
Genome-wide Methylation Dynamics and Context-dependent Gene Expression
Variability in Differentiating Preadipocytes

Binduma Yadav^{1,2,4}, Dalwinder Singh^{1,3,4}, Shrikant Mantri^{1*}, Vikas Rishi^{1*}

List of supplemental items:

Figure S1: Summary of WGBS sequencing read counts of undifferentiated pre-adipocytes (Pre-AD) and differentiated (4H, 2D, and 15D post differentiation).

Figure S2: Schematic diagram of the steps for Whole genome Bisulphite Sequencing (WGBS) and pipeline for data analysis, and associated data analysis programs.

Figure S3: Chromosome-wise DNA methylation pattern depicting various time points during pre-adipocyte differentiation.

Figure S4: qRT-PCR analysis: Bar graphs showing qRT-PCR analysis of various adipogenic genes such as DNMT3A, DNMT3B, DNMT1, MBD1, MBD2, MBD3, MBD4, MeCP21, MeCP2 2, UHRF1, UHRF2, CBX5.

Figure S5: Idiograms depicting the DMRs distribution on chromosomes. A) Hyper-DMRs at 15D, B) Hyper-DMRs at 2D, C) Hyper-DMRs at 4H, D) Hypo-DMRs at 15D, E) Hypo-DMRs at 2D, F) Hypo-DMRs at 4H.

Figure S6: Pearson Correlation between NABI control vs. AR control. Total locations of NABI control with coverage 10:29584. Total locations of AR pre-adipocyte with coverage 10: 32860286. Common locations used for correlation analysis: 28973.

Figure S7: Comparison of NABI & AR data. Red color indicates pre-adipocytes and green represents the adipocytes whereas blue indicates NABI control.

Figure S8: Hypermethylation at *Lyz2* promoter at terminally differentiated adipocytes.

Table S1: List of Oligos used in the study for performing qRT-PCR to check adipogenic gene expression.

Table S2: GO pathway analysis. GO enrichment analysis of genes whose promoter overlapped with DMRs. For GO analysis, genes were grouped into different functional categories: biological process (BP), Cellular component (CC), and Molecular Function (MF).

KEGG pathway analysis enrichKEGG of clusterProfiler is used for pathway analysis with BH procedure and (final parametric values will be after results are fixed pvalueCutoff = 1, pAdjustMethod = "BH", minGSSize = 1, maxGSSize = 500, qvalueCutoff = 1)

(https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/13U_tKgUZ1KAUxRFsnBY8WN7UT46Z6ixS/edit?usp=sharing&ouid=106034465131344413756&rtpof=true&sd=true)

Table S3: Summary of AR WGBS dataset and read counts in pre-adipocytes and adipocytes depicting increased methylated CpGs as the pre-adipocytes differentiated. A) Mapping of raw reads with reference genome mm10. B) Total analysis of methylated cytosine showing CG cytosines and non-CG cytosines.

Table S4: Correlation analysis at various depths (from 4 to 12) for NABI control vs AR control.

Table S5: Comparison of methylation-dependent gene expression analysis of DMRs present at 2D and 15D; 15D depicting increased expression of certain pathways involved in dedifferentiation.

Comparative analysis between the AR (Adipogenic reprogramming) dataset vs. the NABI dataset

The NABI Whole genome bisulphite sequencing data referred to as the NABI dataset in the subsequent text was compared with the Adipogenic reprogramming dataset (AR dataset,[1]) to validate the results for the analysis of data in terms of whole genome and for comparison of NABI Sanger sequencing data of NIH 3T3L1. The total methylated CpG percentage varies by around 2-4% in completely differentiated adipocytes compared to pre-adipocytes (**Figure S1 & Table S3**) confirmed by both datasets. The bisulphite conversion rate was approximately the same in both cases. The mapping rate was also the same i.e. around 74% in all the cases except 2 days, around 85% (**FigureS1C & TableS3A**).

Correlation analysis between AR and NABI dataset

The evidence from the AR dataset suggests that unique DNA methylation establishes cellular identity, and our study supports this notion. In both studies, WGBS is used to investigate the dynamics of DNA methylation during adipocyte differentiation. The correlation between AR dataset and NABI dataset control is also evident which is 0.94 (**Figure S6**). At the early stage of adipogenesis, DNA methylation was specifically decreased at adipogenesis-related genomic loci which is quite evident in both the studies. The circos plot (**Figure S7**) depicts the chromosome-wise overlap.

The high correlation between AR and NABI data validates the significance of NABI data. The higher the depth, the higher the correlation was found (**Table S4**).

Given the resemblances we found between both the datasets, suggest DNA methylation plays a major regulatory mechanism during the differentiation of preadipocytes.

A

Sample	Raw Reads	Clean Reads	Base quality Q20 (%)	Base quality Q30 (%)	GC (%)	Reads having 50% bases with quality <20 (%)	Reads having 50% bases with quality < 30 (%)
Pre-AD	55,438,326	53,411,178	96.55	89.94	20.08	0	0.15
4H	51,941,175	42,412,105	97.33	91.54	20.16	0	0.32
2D	55,463,283	53,311,291	96.38	89.59	21.14	0	0.14
15D	52,949,471	49,723,797	95.39	87.47	20.04	0	0.17

B

	Pre-AD	4H	2D	15D
Number of Reads aligned to Lambda Genome after de-duplication removal	522,924	420,562	432,252	657,646
Total Cytosines analysed	4,288,500	3,488,969	3,612,914	5,080,239
Total methylated Cytosines	30,682	23,772	24,187	38,216
Total unmethylated Cytosines	4,257,818	3,465,197	3,588,727	5,042,023
Bisulfite Conversion Efficiency (%)	99.285	99.319	99.331	99.248

C

Sample	Total Reads	Mapped Reads	Mapping Rate (%)	Duplicated reads	De-duplication rate (%)	Reads for methylation extraction
Pre-AD	53,411,178	39,346,076	73.66	7,821,993	19.88	31,523,935
4H	42,412,105	31,456,049	74.17	5,687,201	18.08	25,768,684
2Days	53,311,291	45,153,417	84.70	8,364,937	18.53	36,788,357
15Days	49,723,797	36,544,292	73.49	8,580,592	23.48	27,963,323

D

Sample	Total no. of Cs analysed	Methylated Cs in CpG context	Unmethylated Cs in CpG context	mCpG (%)	mCHG (%)	mCHH (%)
Pre-AD	1,608,609,236	41,240,654	27,786,970	59.75	0.86	0.85
4H	1,319,747,325	33,756,587	22,922,625	59.60	0.83	0.82
2Days	1,862,473,519	47,729,004	31,668,170	60.11	0.82	0.81
15Days	1,425,151,215	38,393,366	22,286,277	63.27	0.94	0.95

Figure S1: Summary of WGBS sequencing read counts of undifferentiated pre-adipocytes (Pre-AD) and differentiated (4H, 2D, and 15D post differentiation). Bismark was used for paired-end mapping. Duplicated reads were removed using the deduplicate_bismark command. The genome-wide cytosine analysis was performed using the remaining reads. The methylation bias in the reads was determined with the `-mbias` option of Bismark Methylation Extractor; consequently, methylated CpGs were extracted. **(A)** Raw reads and their cleaning with Trimmomatic **(B)** Clean data was mapped to mouse genome mm10 by Bismark pipeline. Average coverage > 1x at each cytosine site. **(C)** Mapping of raw reads with reference genome mm10. **(D)** Total analysis of methylated cytosine showing CG cytosines and non-CG cytosines.

Figure S2: Schematic diagram of the steps for Whole genome Bisulphite Sequencing (WGBS) and pipeline for data analysis, and associated data analysis programs. FASTQ files generated from raw WGBS data were aligned with reference genome using Bismark. Output bam files were further processed through the remainder of the workflow pipeline.

Figure S3: Chromosome-wise DNA methylation pattern depicting various time points during pre-adipocyte differentiation to mature adipocytes. X-axis: DNA methylation percentage. Y-axis- depicts Transcription start site (TSS), Transcription end site (TES), gene body, and promoter region.

Figure S4: qRT-PCR analysis: Bar graphs showing qRT-PCR analysis of various adipogenic genes such as DNMT3A, DNMT3B, DNMT1, MBD1, MBD2, MBD3, MBD4, MeCP2 1, MeCP2 2, UHRF1, UHRF2, CBX5.

Figure S5: Idiograms depicting the DMRs distribution on chromosomes. A) Hyper-DMRs at 15D, B) Hyper-DMRs at 2D, C) Hyper-DMRs at 4H, D) Hypo-DMRs at 15D, E) Hypo-DMRs at 2D, F) Hypo-DMRs at 4H.

Figure S6: Pearson Correlation between NABI control vs. AR control. Total locations of NABI control with coverage 10:29584. Total locations of AR pre-adipocyte with coverage 10:32860286. Common locations used for correlation analysis: 28973.

Figure S7: Comparison of NABI & AR data. Red color indicates pre-adipocytes and green represents the adipocytes whereas blue indicates NABI control.

Figure S8: Hypermethylation at *Lyz2* promoter at terminally differentiated adipocytes.

Table S1: Primers used for qRT-PCR.

Adipogenic Genes		
KLF5	Forward Primer	GGCTCTCCCCGAGTTCACTA
	Reverse Primer	ATTACTGCCGTCTGGTTTGTC
KLF6	Forward Primer	GTTTCTGCTCGGACTCCTGAT
	Reverse Primer	TTCCTGGAAGATGCTACACATTG
STAT5a	Forward Primer	CAGCCGTGGGATGCTATTGA
	Reverse Primer	GGGACAGCGGTCATACGTG
ZFP423	Forward Primer	TGGCCTGGGATTCCTCTGT
	Reverse Primer	CTCTTGACTTGTCACGCTGTT
ZFP467	Forward Primer	TCCTGCTCAGGGCATGAGA
	Reverse Primer	TCCGAATCATCCATTCCTCCC
Tcf711 variant1	Forward Primer	CGTCCCTGGTCAACGAATCG
	Reverse Primer	CTTCTCACTTCGGCGAAATAGT
Tcf711 variant2	Forward Primer	ACGAGCTGATCCCCTTCCA
	Reverse Primer	CAGGGACGACTTGACCTCAT
KLF2	Forward Primer	GAGCCTATCTTGCCGTCCTTT
	Reverse Primer	CACGTTGTTTAGGTCCTCATCC
Foxo1	Forward Primer	CCCAGGCCGGAGTTTAACC
	Reverse Primer	GTTGCTCATAAAGTCGGTGCT
Foxa2	Forward Primer	TCCGACTGGAGCAGCTACTAC
	Reverse Primer	GCGCCACATAGGATGACA
Foxc2	Forward Primer	AACCCAACAGCAAACCTTCCC
	Reverse Primer	GCGTAGCTCGATAGGGCAG
CD36	Forward Primer	ATGGGCTGTGATCGGAACTG

	Reverse Primer	TTTGCCACGTCATCTGGGTTT
Lipoprotein lipase	Forward Primer	ATGGATGGACGGTAACGGGAA
	Reverse Primer	CCCGATAACAACCAGTCTACTACA
Fasn	Forward Primer	GGAGGTGGTGATAGCCGGTAT
	Reverse Primer	TGGGTAATCCATAGAGCCCAG
Plin1	Forward Primer	CTGTGTGCAATGCCTATGAGA
	Reverse Primer	CTGGAGGGTATTGAAGAGCCG
Plin5	Forward Primer	CTTCCTGCCCATGACTGAGG
	Reverse Primer	GACCCAGACGCACAAAGTAG
Plin2	Forward Primer	GACCTTGTGTCCTCCGCTTAT
	Reverse Primer	CAACCGCAATTTGTGGCTC
Plin3	Forward Primer	ATGTCTAGCAATGGTACAGATGC
	Reverse Primer	CGTGGAAGTATAAGAGGCAGG
Plin4	Forward Primer	GTGTCCACCAACTCACAGATG
	Reverse Primer	GGACCATTCTTTTGCAGCAT
Plin5 variant1	Forward Primer	TGTCCAGTGCTTACAACCTCGG
	Reverse Primer	CAGGGCACAGGTAGTCACAC
Plin1 variant1	Forward Primer	GGACCTGTGAGTGCTTCC
	Reverse Primer	GTATTGAAGAGCCGGGATCTTTT
Dgat1	Forward Primer	CTGATCCTGAGTAATGCAAGGTT
	Reverse Primer	TGGATGCAATAATCACGCATGG
Angptl4	Forward Primer	CATCCTGGGACGAGATGAACT
	Reverse Primer	TGACAAGCGTTACCACAGGC
PDGFR α	Forward Primer	TATCCTCCCAAACGAGAATGAGA

	Reverse Primer	GTGGTTGTAGTAGCAAGTGTACC
PDGFR β variant1	Forward Primer	AGGAGTGATACCAGCTTTAGTCC
	Reverse Primer	CCGAGCAGGTCAGAACAAAGG
PDGFR β variant2	Forward Primer	TTCCAGGAGTGATACCAGCTT
	Reverse Primer	AGGGGGCGTGATGACTAGG
VEGFc	Forward Primer	GTGAGGTGTGTATAGATGTGGGG
	Reverse Primer	ACGTCTTGCTGAGGTAACCTG
VEGFb	Forward Primer	GCCAGACAGGGTTGCCATAC
	Reverse Primer	GGAGTGGGATGGATGATGTCAG
EGR2	Forward Primer	CCAGACACTACTTTCCACCG
	Reverse Primer	CCTCCCAGTTCACCATTGGG
Resistin	Forward Primer	CAGGTCGCTTCCTGATGTCG
	Reverse Primer	CCAGACCCTCAGCTTAGACC
Lpl(154)	Forward Primer	AGGCATACAGGTGCAACTCC
	Reverse Primer	TAGGGCATCTGAGAGCGAGT
Fabp4	Forward Primer	TAAAAGTGAGCTATCTGGACTTCA
	Reverse Primer	GCCCACTCCCCTTCTTTCAT
CREB1	Forward Primer	GAGAAGCGGAGTGTTGGTGA
	Reverse Primer	ACTCTGCTGGTTGTCTGCTC
TET1 variant1	Forward Primer	GCAGTGAACCCCGGAAAAC
	Reverse Primer	AGAGCCATTGTAAACCCGTTG
TET1 variant2	Forward Primer	ACACAGTGGTGCTAATGCAG
	Reverse Primer	AGCATGAACGGGAGAATCGG
TET2	Forward Primer	CTCCCATCAGCCATACAGAACC

	Reverse Primer	CTGACTGTGCGTTTTATCCCT
TET3	Forward Primer	TGCGATTGTGTGTCGAACAAATAGT
	Reverse Primer	TCCATACCGATCCTCCATGAG
ADIPOQ	Forward Primer	ATCTGGAGGTGGGAGACCAA
	Reverse Primer	GGGCTATGGGTAGTTGCAGT
GATA2	Forward Primer	CACCCCGCCGTATTGAATG
	Reverse Primer	CCTGCGAGTCGAGATGGTTG
EBF1	Forward Primer	AAGCATCCAACGGAGTGGAAG
	Reverse Primer	GATTTCCGCAGGTTAGAAGGC
Hoxa6	Forward Primer	CGGCCAGGACTCCTTCTTG
	Reverse Primer	CCGAGTTGGACTGTTGGTAAAA
Hoxa5	Forward Primer	CTCATTTTGCGGTCGCTATCC
	Reverse Primer	ATCCATGCCATTGTAGCCGTA
Vdr	Forward Primer	GAATGTGCCTCGGATCTGTGG
	Reverse Primer	ATGCGGCAATCTCCATTGAAG
KLF4	Forward Primer	GGCGAGTCTGACATGGCTG
	Reverse Primer	GCTGGACGCAGTGTCTTCTC
ATF7	Forward Primer	ATCATTGCAGATCAAACGCCT
	Reverse Primer	AGCACCCCTTTTTCTCATCGTC
JunB	Forward Primer	TCACGACGACTCTTACGCAG
	Reverse Primer	CCTTGAGACCCCGATAGGGA
Pbx1 Variant a	Forward Primer	CAGCGGGTTCTTCCAGTTCTT
	Reverse Primer	CGAGTCCGTCACTGTATCCTC
Pbx1 Variant b	Forward Primer	TGAAGCCTGCCTTGTTTAATGT

	Reverse Primer	ATGTTGTCCAGTCGCATGAGC
Slc2a1	Forward Primer	TACACCCCAGAACCAATGGC
	Reverse Primer	CCCGTAGCTCAGATCGTCAC
Lyz2(NM_017372.3)	Forward Primer	AGCACACTGTCAAAACCGAG
	Reverse Primer	CTTAGAGGGGAAATCGAGGGAA
Lyz2(17105)	Forward Primer	TGCCAGAACTCTGAAAAGGAATGG
	Reverse Primer	CAGTGCTTTGGTCTCCACGGTT
GM14325 (NM_001024849.3)	Forward Primer	CCATAAATGCATTCAATATGGGGA
	Reverse Primer	ACATTTCTTGTATCCCCTTGA ACT
GM10354 (NM_001281514.1)	Forward Primer	CAAAGAGATCCAGCTCACTATGGA
	Reverse Primer	GGGATTTTGCCTGTGGTAGGG

A)

Samples	Raw reads	Filter and Trim reads	Clean ratio	Mapped reads	Mapping Rate (%)	Duplicated reads	Duplicated Rate (%)
Adipocyte	870974927	870967170	99.07	648845222	74.5	63739281	9.82
Preadipocyte	891784966	891779716	99.07	666335293	74.72	61245031	9.19

B)

Samples	Total Cytosine	Methylated CpG	Unmethylated CpG	mCpG (%)	mCHG (%)	mCHH (%)
Adipocyte	24688537793	797818959	454925272	63.69	0.13	0.18
Preadipocytes	25172225618	834519959	449432824	65	0.11	0.15

Table S3: Summary of AR WGBS dataset and read counts in pre-adipocytes and adipocytes depicting increased methylated CpGs as the pre-adipocytes differentiated. A) Mapping of raw reads with reference genome mm10. B) Total analysis of methylated cytosine showing CG cytosines and non-CG cytosines.

Read Depth	Correlation(NABI vs AR)	Common CpG locations
4	0.866957	2830772
5	0.8808512	1057385
6	0.89205	379097
7	0.9050764	141414
8	0.9194332	63271
9	0.9312149	37840
10	0.9397303	28973
11	0.9437549	25454
12	0.9469991	23563

Table S4: Correlation analysis at various depths (from 4 to 12) for NABI control vs AR control.

Hyper 15D	Hyper 2D	Hypo 15D	Hypo 2D
Negative regulation of cytokine production	mucopolysaccharide metabolic process	erythrocyte differentiation	ruffle assembly
nucleoside monophosphate biosynthetic process	mitochondrial transmembrane transport	regulation of fat cell differentiation	apoptotic process involved in the development
positive regulation of interleukin-12 production	nitric oxide biosynthetic process	regulation of protein localization to the nucleus	regulation of extrinsic apoptotic signaling pathway in the absence of ligand
cellular detoxification	regulation of osteoclast differentiation	establishment of cell polarity	spliceosomal complex assembly
glycogen biosynthetic process	cellular response to unfolded protein	regeneration	response to light stimulus
glucan biosynthetic process	regulation of multicellular organism growth	kidney epithelium development	response to pH
positive regulation of mitotic nuclear division	proteoglycan metabolic process	regulation of osteoblast differentiation	apoptotic cell clearance
intestinal absorption	nitric oxide metabolic process	nephron development	positive regulation of G1/S transition of mitotic cell cycle
cellular response to lipopolysaccharide	negative regulation of myeloid cell differentiation	erythrocyte homeostasis	negative regulation of the production of molecular mediators of immune response
regulation of macrophage cytokine production	intermediate filament cytoskeleton organization	negative regulation of the Wnt signaling pathway	mitotic spindle checkpoint signaling
positive regulation of protein tyrosine kinase activity	killing of cells of another organism	regulation of ubiquitin-dependent protein catabolic process	establishment of protein localization to the endoplasmic reticulum
regulation of polysaccharide metabolic process	intermediate filament-based process	cellular response to starvation	negative regulation of intracellular protein transport

toll-like receptor 4 signaling pathway	sulfur compound biosynthetic process	signal transduction in response to DNA damage	regulation of TORC1 signaling
positive regulation of signaling receptor activity	regulation of oxidoreductase activity	BMP signaling pathway	regulation of fibroblast migration
cellular response to molecule of bacterial origin	establishment of protein localization to mitochondrion	protein import into nucleus	regulation of peptidyl-threonine phosphorylation
mRNA polyadenylation	cyclic-nucleotide-mediated signaling	regulation of response to wounding	biological phase
positive regulation of the glucose metabolic process	inclusion body	hindbrain development	peptidyl-serine phosphorylation
apoptotic cell clearance	Golgi stack	ruffle	negative regulation of dephosphorylation
negative regulation of I-kappa B kinase/NF-kappaB signaling	cortical actin cytoskeleton	focal adhesion	regulation of alcohol biosynthetic process
peptidyl-tyrosine phosphorylation	antioxidant activity	carboxylic acid binding	spindle checkpoint signaling
RNA polyadenylation		phosphatidylinositol phosphate binding	regulation of hormone metabolic process
peptidyl-tyrosine modification			DNA geometric change
regulation of transcription from RNA polymerase II promoter in response to stress			regulation of erythrocyte differentiation
positive regulation of nitric oxide biosynthetic process			regulation of intracellular transport
cellular response to toxic substance			phospholipid translocation
regulation of ERK1 and ERK2 cascade			regulation of mitotic cell cycle phase transition

Golgi apparatus subcompartment			regulation of humoral immune response
scavenger receptor activity			positive regulation of glucose transmembrane transport
MHC class I protein binding			regulation of ubiquitin-protein transferase activity
intramembrane lipid transporter activity			negative regulation of protein phosphorylation
SH2 domain binding			lipid translocation
general transcription initiation factor activity			positive regulation of glial cell differentiation
			histone H3-K9 modification
			neurotransmitter receptor complex
			chloride channel complex
			integral component of mitochondrial inner membrane
			intrinsic component of mitochondrial inner membrane
			cyclin-dependent protein kinase holoenzyme complex
			disulfide oxidoreductase activity

Table S5: Comparison of methylation-dependent gene expression analysis of DMRs present at 2D and 15D; 15D depicting increased expression of certain pathways involved in dedifferentiation.

Supplementary References:

1. J. Park *et al.*, “Targeted erasure of DNA methylation by TET3 drives adipogenic reprogramming and differentiation,” *Nature Metabolism*, vol. 4, no. 7, pp. 918–931, 2022.
2. Emmert Buck *et al.*, “Quantitative RT-PCR gene expression analysis of laser micro-dissected tissue samples,” *Nature Protocols*, vol. 4, pp. 902–922, 2009.